

NEUROMARKETING IN EDUCATION: EMOTIONS AS THE KEY TO SUCCESS

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Abstract: *The article examines the role and importance of neuromarketing in the modern educational process. Special attention is paid to the tools and methods of neuromarketing, their impact on the choice of educational institutions, student engagement and the creation of a sustainable educational brand. The key principles of emotional perception, personalization, and user experience in educational marketing are explored.*

Keywords: *neuromarketing, education, emotional branding, user experience, educational marketing, personalization.*

Introduction. Modern marketing technologies and methods are undergoing significant changes, and one of the key innovations is neuromarketing. In education, neuromarketing helps to better understand the needs of students and applicants, increase their engagement, and create more effective marketing strategies.

Neuromarketing is a field that combines knowledge from neuroscience, psychology, and marketing to analyze and predict human behavior. Its key goal is to understand how emotional and cognitive processes influence decision-making.

Methodology. Renowned scientists in the field of neuromarketing have demonstrated that emotional and cognitive reactions play a crucial role in the perception of marketing messages, which can be effectively applied in educational marketing to improve interaction with the audience.

In particular, M. Lindstrom emphasized the importance of emotional response in decision-making and the influence of sensory perception on consumer choice [2], D.Lewis studied consumer stress reactions and their impact on the perception of marketing messages [3], D. Lowry considered the cognitive aspects of decision-making and their relationship to marketing incentives [4]. According to F. According to Kotler, today neuromarketing has evolved into a full-fledged marketing area. Neuromarketing technology is based on a model according to which the majority (more than 90%) of human mental activity, including emotions, occurs in the subconscious area, that is, below the levels of controlled awareness [1].

Results and discussion. The concept of neuromarketing assumes that a person perceives environmental stimuli (for example, a product presentation) primarily at the level of neurophysiological signals. They are translated by the senses through biophysical and biochemical processes into the language of emotions at the level of the subconscious, the limbic system – the deep subcortex of the brain, which determines the type of emotional system.

The conceptual foundations of neuromarketing include understanding cognitive and emotional decision-making mechanisms, analyzing the perception of advertising and educational messages, and using data to predict audience behavior. Key elements include:

- Emotional response: Analysis of reactions to visual and textual elements of the content.
- Cognitive processes: The study of how information is perceived and processed by the brain.
- Motivation and behavior: Identification of factors influencing the choice of educational programs.
- Personalization of the experience: Adapting content and marketing strategies to individual needs.

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

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These principles allow educational institutions to develop more effective marketing campaigns and improve interaction with the audience.

It should be noted that the most important advantage of neuromarketing over classical marketing is the ability to accurately identify which of the advertised products, brands or videos you just like, and which is really effective for making a decision.

To date, neuromarketing studies have already allowed us to study areas of the brain that are activated in the following situations:

1. When looking at products (including food) or brands that a person prefers.
2. At the moments of trust — whether it's trust in the seller, the product, a loved one, a friend or a family member.
3. When making decisions related to the choice between instant pleasure (for example, buying a product) and immediate disappointment (spending money).
4. In moments of enjoyment or perception of beauty.
5. When a person experiences altruistic feelings.
6. During negotiations, when emotions prevail over rationality or, conversely, when participants maintain cold calculation, suppressing emotional impulses.

With the development of neuropsychology and cognitive sciences, it has been possible to significantly deepen the understanding of higher brain functions. Based on neurophysiology and neuropsychology, behavioral disciplines have emerged that make it possible to study human reactions to advertising stimuli, select optimal color solutions, study the influence of music and fragrances on the subconscious mind, and analyze brain processes related to decision-making, benefit and risk assessment.

To date, about a hundred results of full-fledged studies of consumer behavior using neuroimaging tools have been published. Let's analyze neuromarketing tools and their impact on the educational process. Depending on the cognitive and emotional mechanisms of decision-making, they can be divided into the following groups:

Eye-tracking is a technology that allows you to track and analyze where and for how long a person is looking using special devices that record eye movement. This method helps to understand which elements on advertising materials attract attention and how visual stimuli are perceived.

Facial Coding is a method based on the analysis of microexpressions of a person's face to determine his emotional state in response to various stimuli. This allows you to identify a person's true reaction, for example, to an advertisement, product, or brand, without verbal reporting.

Heat Maps are visual representations of data that show which areas of an image or page are most actively perceived by viewers. The brighter the color, the more attention is paid to this part. This tool helps marketers optimize the placement of ads or content on a website.

Big Data and analytics is the use of large amounts of data obtained from various sources to analyze consumer behavior. The use of sophisticated analytical methods makes it possible to identify patterns in customer preferences, predict trends, and develop more accurate marketing strategies tailored to individual customer needs.

These tools allow you to analyze user reactions to advertising materials, the interface of educational platforms, and other interaction elements.

These factors, acting both individually and in combination, form a subconscious decision among consumers about choosing a particular offer, since they affect subjective perceptions, distracting from

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-5, ISSUE-1

purely rational arguments. Let's look at how key neuromarketing triggers are used to increase sales (Table 1.).

Table 1.

Neuromarketing Triggers

Neuromarketing Triggers	Influence on the subconscious mind
Colour	For example, red concentrates attention, blue relaxes, green calms, and yellow stimulates reflection. Choosing the right color helps to set accents and create the right mood, thanks to which the offer will be perceived as more attractive.
Sound	Noises, music, and sounds of nature can activate positive emotions or motivate you to take action. They can adjust the pace at which customers move around the store, speed up or slow down decision-making, and enhance the experience of buying or receiving a service.
Taste	Combinations of ingredients or ingredients in a recipe can cause specific emotions or even create dependence in the client, influencing his choice.
Smell	Scents, like flowers, can set up a certain emotional perception, evoke the right associations and encourage actions that correspond to marketing goals.
The sense of touch	It's hard to resist buying things that you want to touch all the time. Pleasant tactile sensations can evoke strong emotions, whether during relaxation, beauty treatments, or choosing clothes in a store.
is light	Lighting affects brain activity and mood. Bright light makes jewelry attractive, and soft warm lighting will create an atmosphere of comfort in a furniture store.

Emotions play a key role in the perception of an educational brand. Effective use of storytelling, video content, and student reviews allows you to create a strong emotional connection with an educational institution.

Personalized offers, personalized recommendations, and tailored communications can significantly improve the effectiveness of marketing campaigns in education. At the same time, the collection and use of data requires compliance with ethical standards and transparency. Educational institutions must adhere to the principles of confidentiality and openness in working with data.

Studying the reaction of the target audience can significantly improve the effectiveness of marketing communications, strengthen the emotional connection with brands and, ultimately, have a positive impact on sales. Human emotions determine the areas where neuromarketing tools produce the best results. These include:

- **Branding.** Creating positive associations, improving brand memorability and recognition are the main tasks faced by marketers. As shown in the article, neuromarketing has powerful tools that help to find the most effective solutions and make the choice of a brand natural and intuitive for consumers.
- **Service sector.** In this area, competition mainly takes place at the level of consumer emotions. The most important component of the cost of a service is the impression that a person receives in the

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-5, ISSUE-1

process of receiving it. Thus, the role of neuromarketing in this area is huge and difficult to overestimate.

- **Product design development.** The appearance of a product has long been an important motive for buyers willing to pay for an attractive and recognizable brand. Proper design is not only an aesthetic pleasure of purchase, but also a key factor in successful sales and profit growth of the company.
- **Visualization and location of points of sale.** The transformation of points of sale into attractive spaces for customers, making their purchases more enjoyable, as well as the optimal organization of customer routes, the location of key products and promotions, and the creation of comfortable navigation so that customers can easily find what they need and feel comfortable.
- **Office space design.** Similarly, you can create a positive atmosphere in offices by applying neuromarketing techniques to improve employee mood and productivity.
- **Development of advertising materials, videos, website design and mobile applications.** Why can't the customer or consumer find the information or the "buy" button? Why is it difficult for him to navigate the app? Neuromarketing offers solutions that will help improve the perception of interfaces and enhance the convenience of interacting with products and services.

Examples of the use of neuromarketing in education

1. Universities use emotional videos:

Students' stories about their successes.

Presentation of the campus and its unique characteristics.

2. Online platforms introduce personalized recommendations:

A course offered based on the user's interests.

Using push notifications for reminders and motivation.

3. Colors and branding:

Well-chosen colors (for example, blue for trust, green for harmony) enhance brand perception.

4. Using urgency and the FOMO effect:

"The number of seats is limited!"

"Sign up before the end of the week and get a discount!"

The use of neuromarketing in education involves the creation of a sustainable educational brand, a strategic approach that combines clear goals, attention to the needs of the target audience, as well as long-term efforts to strengthen reputation and trust. To create a brand of an educational institution, it is necessary:

Determine the uniqueness of the educational institution. To create a sustainable brand, it is important to understand how this educational institution stands out from others. These can be special educational programs, innovative teaching methods, highly qualified teaching staff, or a unique atmosphere. Clearly defining and emphasizing these aspects will help you stand out from the competition.

Establish clear brand values and mission. The brand of an educational institution should be based on clear values that will be attractive to students, parents and teachers. The mission and values of an educational institution should reflect the approach to learning and life in an educational institution, which will create trust and emotional attachment.

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-5, ISSUE-1

Use neuromarketing to connect emotionally with your audience. Emotional attachment plays an important role in building a sustainable brand. Neuromarketing helps you use visual, audiovisual, and sensory elements to form positive associations with your brand. The inclusion of these elements in student engagement campaigns or in educational interactions will help strengthen emotional connection.

Work on reputation and trust. It is important to actively build and maintain a reputation. Transparency, openness, and responsiveness to feedback from students, parents, and other stakeholders help build trust. The positive feedback and success of your graduates also influence the perception of the brand.

Constant updating and innovation. A sustainable educational brand requires constant updating and adaptation. This may include the introduction of new technologies in education, adaptation to modern labor market requirements and student interests. A brand that does not stand still, while remaining relevant, arouses interest and retains loyalty.

Visual and communication identity. An important part of a sustainable brand is its visual identity: the logo, colors, fonts, and other elements that create an unforgettable image of the educational institution. In addition, it is important to maintain the consistency of communication through all channels: website, social networks, advertising materials.

Create a network of partnerships and strengthen the community. A sustainable educational brand is also built through relationships with external partners: businesses, government and educational institutions. It is also important to keep in touch with graduates and form an active and supportive community that promotes the brand through word of mouth.

Effectiveness assessment and strategy adaptation. Regular monitoring of the success of the educational institution's branding efforts helps to adjust the strategy. Assessing how a brand is perceived, what works, and what needs to be changed helps ensure its long-term attractiveness and stability.

Creating a sustainable educational brand is a complex process that requires time, effort, and a careful approach to the needs of the target audience. The strategy must be flexible in order to adapt to changes in the educational environment and society as a whole.

Conclusions. Thus, the use of neuromarketing in educational institutions increases the effectiveness of marketing campaigns, increases brand credibility, improves user experience, increases student engagement, and plays a key role in modern educational marketing, helping educational institutions better understand their students, build trust, and improve interaction. It is a powerful tool that, if used correctly, can significantly improve the quality of educational marketing and strengthen the brand of an educational institution.

To implement neuromarketing, educational organizations must invest in analytics and research of user behavior, create emotionally intense marketing campaigns, optimize user experience on all platforms, implement personalized approaches to each student, and be transparent in data collection and use.

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